

University of Oradea
Faculty of Environmental Protection

International Symposium

***“SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: CHALLENGES AND
OPPORTUNITIES” & CELEBRATION OF
”30 YEARS OF HIGHER EDUCATION AT THE FACULTY
OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION, UNIVERSITY OF
ORADEA”***

November 09-10, 2023
Oradea, Romania

TIMETABLE

09. November 2023 – Elite Conference Room, Oradea

- 9.30** Registration
- 10.00** Opening Ceremony – Welcome Speech – Ass. Prof. **Cristina MAERESCU**, PhD, Dean, Faculty of Environmental Protection, University of Oradea
- 10.15** Speaker - Prof. habil. **Constantin BUNGĂU**, PhD, Rector, University of Oradea
- 10.30** **Teodor Eugen Man**
Irrigation - Past, Present and Future, Case Study: Numerical Modeling, Mike 11 Program, for Calculating the Volume of Water Available from Drainage for Irrigation
- 10.50** **Mihai COVACI, Radu Petru BREJEA, Brindusa COVACI, Carmen CATUNA, Adriana CIOTEA**
Precision Agriculture Index: A Green Mountain Entrepreneurship Paradigm
- 11.10** **Alin MOȘ**
- 11.40** Apuseni Natural Park, a Park for Nature and People
Adelina VENIG, Aurora VENIG, Olimpia IORDĂNESCU
Research Regarding the Influence of Grafting Moment on the Quality and Quantity of the Cherry Tree Planting Material
- 12.00** **Alin Cristian TEUSDEA, Livia BANDICI, Vasile Darie ȘOPRONI, Francisc Ioan HATHAZI, Mircea Nicoleae ARION, Carmen Otilia MOLNAR, Simona Ioana VICAS**
Plant Extract with Assisted High Frequency Electromagnetic Field (MicroWave)
- 12.30** Coffee break
- 13.00** The 30th Anniversary Celebration of Higher Education at the Faculty of Environmental Protection
- 16.00** Official dinner (Elite Restaurant, Oradea)

10. November 2023 – University of Oradea, Faculty of Environmental Protection, Oradea

- 10.00 – 12.00 – Ceremony of Awarding the Doctor Honoris Causa title to Professor Sorin Mihai CĂMPEANU, PhD
Location: Aula Magna of the University of Oradea
- 13.00 – 18.00 – Scientific Symposium- Presentation of Scientific Papers/ Poster
- 18.00 Departure